

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: ATIASE****FIRST NAME: BRIGHT****PROGRAM CODE: DME****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: **xx%**

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 11)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Writing academic essay (EUCLID 2021, 7-11)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 34-37)
3. American vs. British English (EUCLID 2021, 25-32)
4. Punctuations (EUCLID 2021, 16-22)
5. Style guide and its importance (EUCLID 2021, 41-42)
6. Abbreviations and acronyms (EUCLID 2021, 44 & 59-64)

ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING BASICS

1) INTRODUCTION

When I first read the preface and the course contents of the ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack (Period 1), I immediately said to myself confidently that these were lessons I learned during my secondary school days and may not need it as a Doctoral student. After going through the document from chapters one to eight, I came to the conclusion that I told myself a lie because I was convinced that I knew very little about the technicalities underpinning most of the topics discussed in the document.

In reading through the ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack (Period 1), I came to the realization that the content, coupled with the 14 minutes short video tutorial I watched on the LMS portal was to sharpen my communication and academic writing skills. I have unlearned some old-fashioned ways of writing, and through this course, I have learned new ideas.

For a very long time, I was inclined towards the use of the British style of writing in English because I was taught many years ago that the British were our colonial masters

and, for that matter, we must emulate their English language standards. However, after reading the course pack, I discovered that the American English Language is more widely used than the British (EUCLID 2021, 25). With this in mind, I have resolved that I would be writing more using the American English language standards in order to master its use.

This response paper expounded on various areas to consider when writing standard academic essays. I discussed in this response paper what to consider when writing an academic essay. I also touched on the proper and consistent use of the two acceptable English language writing styles – American and British. Proper ways of punctuating a sentence or a phrase and plagiarism and its adverse effect on academic essay writing were also discussed. In addition, I discuss the proper use of abbreviations and acronyms when dealing with academic essay writing.

2) WRITING AN ACADEMIC ESSAY

Unlike other types of essays, scholarly essay writing is not based on fiction, but it is based on research evidence that may or may not be published. I have noted there are systematic processes involved when putting academic essays together, and one must always adhere to them in order to produce a high-quality academic essay.

When planning to embark on the journey of writing a scholarly essay, one has to draft an initial plan (include your thoughts about the research problem you seek to address) outlining the basic steps on how to go about the entire academic essay writing. For example, in commencing an academic essay, one must start early enough to read around the research topic (literature review) and also start with a zero draft of the paper, having in mind the research question (EUCLID 2021, 7). This is particularly important because most of the research topics are not new; hence, one needs to do thorough reading to understand the extent of research that has already been conducted by other researchers in the area of your research in order to have a balanced viewpoint from different authors.

It is worth noting that the structure of every academic essay should fall under three broad categories – introduction, the main body of the essay, and conclusion (EUCLID 2021, 10). The aim of structuring the essay is to promote uniformity and also make reviews and reading easier for others. The introductory section deals with the general to specific issues relating to the topic under research and also gives a clear indication of how the entire essay is structured. The body of the essay is where you build your arguments to answer the research questions through discussions. In concluding an essay, one should not introduce new ideas but rather conclude on the issues that were discussed in the paper.

For effective academic essay writing, one must organize the into paragraphs and sections with relevant examples drawn from the subject area under research. I support the argument made by (EUCLID 2021, 11) that the draft academic essay should be kept aside for a few days to allow for fresh ideas and iteration reviews (proofread) by the author and his or her peers.

3) PLAGIARISM

According to EUCLID (2021, 34), plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information. I learned that there are two ways one can fall prey to plagiarism. The first one is when one uses the words of a source without quotation marks, and one should either use the exact words with quotation marks or restate the point in your own words. Second, if you take another author's ideas from a source without appropriately footnoting the source will amount to plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 14). Both of these forms are unethical and unacceptable, and it is a clear form of academic dishonesty when writing an academic essay.

I am aware that plagiarizing someone else's work is a serious offense and must be avoided at all times during academic essay writing. Hence, the source must be properly acknowledged whenever one uses information from other sources rather than one's own constructs. I support the argument that one must properly cite or credit authors when using quotes, paraphrases, data, or visuals borrowed from another source (EUCLID 2021, 34).

Plagiarizing documents is a common mistake some writers commit, but one must be aware of its severity, which may lead to serious consequences. I found it very exciting that EUCLID has taken it upon itself to educate us about how to properly cite documents of other people's work in order not to fall victim to plagiarism.

4) PROPER USE OF AMERICAN VS. BRITISH ENGLISH

As I have already stated in the introductory section of this response paper, I was inclined towards the use of the British style of writing in English because I was taught many years ago that Ghana was under the British colony, and for that matter, we must emulate their English language standards. However, after reading the course pack, I discovered that the American English Language is more widely used than the British (EUCLID 2021, 25).

I noted that the main difference between American and British English is about the house. Some words are spelled and punctuated, and the names of objects (e.g., petrol vs. gasoline, saloon vs. sedan, estate car vs. station wagon, Mr vs Mr., etc.) (EUCLID 2021, 28). After reading the course pack, I realized that I have been using both the American and British English language styles interchangeably in the past years of writing reports and other documents. For the first time in my life and through the reading of the course pack, I have learned the proper use of inverted commas (‘’) and quotation marks (“”).

EUCLID advised that one should decide from the onset of writing an academic essay which version of the English language style – Standard American English (SAE) or Standard British English (SBE) to adopt in order to conform to EUCLID's standards way of presenting essays. EUCLID however recommends the use of Standard American English for academic essays (EUCLID 2021, 41).

5) PUNCTUATIONS

I have noted that using punctuation marks is very important in our everyday writing and reading because it helps us retain the meaning of the sentence one is communicating. The use of punctuation marks, such as full stops, commas, semi-colons, brackets, quotation marks, apostrophes, and hyphens, are used in academic essays to separate sentences in order to clarify the meaning of a piece of text to be understood (EUCLID 2021, 16–23).

I would argue that without properly punctuating a sentence, the very essence of the sentence would be lost to different interpretations. It is, therefore, very crucial for one to pay attention to the use of punctuation marks when writing academic essays. For instance, one needs to know when to use the single quotation mark and when to use the double quotation mark when presenting an academic essay. Also, proper usage of commas, apostrophes, brackets, bullet points, colon and semicolon, hyphens and so on, within the context of an academic essay is encouraged by EUCLID. However, EUCLID warned against the use of apostrophes (e.g., don't, can't, couldn't, etc.) when dealing with scholarly essays.

6) STYLE GUIDE AND ITS IMPORTANCE

According to EUCLID (2021, 41), a style guide is a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent and are generally associated with certain types of writing, for example, technical writing, commercial or business writing, journalism, and web copywriting.

I have noted that one very important reason to adhere to guidelines is to ensure that the voice and style of a piece of writing is consistent, even when it is written by multiple authors. By meticulously following guidelines, one can ensure that their work is consistent and more cohesive with the overall style of the publication.

Even though one may get the rules of punctuation and grammar right in an academic essay, the style goes beyond punctuation and grammar to include preferred sentence lengths, manuscript layout, font usage, depth of treatment of a subject, spelling format, readership considerations, and many more (EUCLID 2021, 41). Reading through the BBC News online Style Guide (BBC 2023), I noted many simple errors committed daily in both oral and written communications. I noted that words and phrases such as advance warning, armed gunmen, universal panacea, mutual co-operation, crew members, history, AN exact replica, anti-government rebel forces, and pre-planned weather conditions are complete tautology and must be avoided.

Thankfully, EUCLID has recommended for its students to use Turabian style as it preferred choice. Accordingly, the response paper template has been formatted to accommodate some aspects of the Chicago Manual of Style format. This particularly makes formatting the response paper much easier because the main heading, sub-headings, paragraphing, and the body of the paper are preset for use.

7) CONCLUSION

The maiden session of the Ph.D. journey was an eye-opener for me because of the many mistakes I had committed in the past in report writing and oral communication. I have come to a complete realization that I need to do more to improve my oral and writing skills. I promised to read through the course pack again in my leisure time. I can confidently confirm that learning is truly a continuous activity as long as one is alive. Based on the knowledge I have acquired through reading the course pack, I resolve that henceforward, I will be mindful of how I present subsequent academic essays and improve my oral communications.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui: Euclid University.

Cleenewerck, Laurent, director. 2021. *Basic ACA-401/ACA-401D Tutorial*. Vimeo.

BBC News Style Guide. 2023: "Grammar, Spelling and Punctuation." Accessed October 15, 2023.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.